

Land Use Transformations Project (JHI-C3-1)
Milestone 25 – LU/LUC story telling draft findings
Internal Report

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1 Context

This milestone indicates progress in the research activity C3.2 “Jointed up approaches to managing land”: Land Use/Land Use Change Story Telling.

1.1 Preceding and subsequent milestones and deliverables:

- M8 Purposive sample for story-telling finalised (Oct 2022)
- M9 Sensory and conventional interview analytical approach confirmed (Feb 2023)
- M25: LU/LUC story telling draft findings fed into QST2 (Sep 2023)
- D9 Digital Story on different views on LU/LUC (May 2024)
- M39: LU/LUC Story Telling findings fed into QST 3 (June 2025)
- M49: New/Alternative Land Use Stories (January 2026)
- D14: New/Alternative Land Use Stories (February 2027)

2 Overview of the research process:

The overall research plan is to identify a diverse set of voices which are weighing in on land-related issues in Scotland and assess the visions of land futures that these voices present.

1. Whose voices are put forward in land sector governance consultations?
2. What vision of land futures do these voices present?
3. What undesirable land futures do these voices argue against?
4. What environmental and/or social justice issues are expressed in these responses?
5. Which voices are missing from these consultation processes?
6. On what grounds do consultation voices claim legitimacy?

For the previous milestone (M9), 15 organisations were selected from a diverse range of stakeholders that responded to a selection of land-related Scottish Government consultations (see Milestone 9 report, February 2023, for more details).

	Support for Agriculture and the Rural Economy Post-Brexit 2018	National Council of Rural Advisers 2018	Rural Assets Strategy 2019	Good Food Nation 2019	Right to Buy Land 2019	Environmental Principles and Governance 2019	Scottish Crown Estate 2019	Forestry Strategy 2019/2029	Scotland's Economic Performance 2020	Review of Mental Health Law 2020	Climate Change Net Zero Nation 2020	Agricultural Transition in Scotland 2021	Scotland's Third Land Use Strategy	Environmental Standards Scotland 2022	Draft National Planning Framework 4 2022	Land Rights and Responsibilities Statement 2022
Community Land Scotland	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
Community Woodlands Association	*			*			*		*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
Paths for All	*					*	*		*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
Creative Scotland									*	*				*		
Quakers in Scotland									*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
Historic Environment Scotland	*	*		*		*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
Royal Town Planning Institute		*		*		*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
Highlands and Islands Enterprise				*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
Scottish Environment LINK	*		*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
John Muir Trust		*			*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
Scottish Land and Estates	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
National Farmers Union				*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
Scottish Crofting Federation	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
CONFOR	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
Soil Association Scotland	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*

The organisations’ responses to 17 select consultations (109 total responses) were coded using NVivo qualitative data analysis software according to a framework based on Carvalho’s 2000 media analysis methodology. We then created a template in which to summarize each organisation’s responses to the

consultations to share with them for subsequent interviews. Our focus encompassed the issues Sonnino et al. (2016) identified as critical to governance frameworks: “the role attributed to different food system actors, their diverse views of rights and responsibility, and the types of interactions that are prioritised to achieve collective goals” (p. 477). These summaries were augmented by publicly available information about the organisation’s overall aims, funding sources, and the scale and scope of their work. Finally, we carried out a comparative-synchronic analysis¹ (Carvalho, 2000) of the various representations of land use by concerned organisations in the 4-year span of consultation submissions studied.

Following the textual analysis of the consultations (reported here), we will aim to conduct at least 10 interviews with representatives across the above organisations (from October 2023). They will be asked to review the templates for accordance with their organisation’s views and goals. To further understand the visions that these organisations have for land use in Scotland, we will ask about significant changes to land use that they’ve seen during their tenure with the organisation, significant achievements of the organisation in regard to land use, their vision for 20 years from now, their concerns, and the steps the organisation will take to achieve the vision. This will give us data to further refine our analysis.

3 Interim findings

The responses to the consultations can be seen as performances for a (government) audience, persuasive texts (Ewick and Silbey, 1995). Responses may employ the government’s chosen framing or vocabulary to show agreement or challenge it. They use persuasive techniques like framing or appealing to values, using various types of supporting evidence and other justifications for their views. These discursive strategies, and the values and norms alluded to, reveal their understandings and assumptions of what land is for, and how its ownership, management, and use should be changed (or kept the same) for a desired rural future.

3.1 What is land for?

Our choice of ‘multifunctionality’ as an analytical framework to look at future land use visions was because of its utility in uncovering different experiences of land and what people value it for. In broad terms, ‘multifunctionality’ refers to the multiple, often intersecting and sometimes contested functions of the countryside. These are broadly inclusive of production (e.g., agricultural commodities, wood products), conservation (e.g., of natural resources) and amenity or consumption (e.g., housing, natural amenities). The multiple functions should offer benefits for humans, for instance, in relation to human health or social cohesion, and likewise secure intact ecological systems (Tzoulas et al. 2007; Laforteza et al. 2013). In this sense, the multifunctionality literature intersects with thinking about ‘ecosystem services’ – the benefits people obtain from ecosystems – and indeed, a Web of Knowledge scan of use of the term ‘multifunctionality’ in the last five years shows significant use of it in conjunction with ecosystems (see Hölting et al. 2019; Garland et al. 2021).

Multifunctionality in the consultation responses is thus more-or-less present, ranging from an acknowledgement of a few functions of land to an in-depth, holistic vision of land’s functions. Interestingly, some organisations seem to see it as something of a blank canvas – Outside the Box portrays it as a space where activities happen, and Paths for All, with its focus on access to land, also views it mainly as a base for recreation, tourism, meetings, and physical activity. Creative Scotland speaks of ‘spaces’ for tourism and wellbeing, including as a venue for events and activities.

Others see it as a resource that provides goods, both public and private. Public goods such as access, aesthetic landscapes, biodiversity, flood protection, carbon sequestration, and other ecosystem services are mentioned

¹ Analysis of various representations of an issue at one point in time – in this case, comparison of organisations’ submissions across each consultation.

by almost every organisation. Sometimes these are referred to vaguely, such as Historical Environment Scotland’s claim that “Inspiring and beneficial landscapes will support economic competitiveness and tourism and will reflect our response to climate change. They provide benefits to our education, health and wellbeing for all” (Just Transition Commission consultation). Other times the benefits are detailed, with certain organisations presenting benefits directly related to their remit. Historic Environment Scotland, for example, often mentions the role of peatland in preserving archaeological artefacts in consultations, and Scottish Land and Estates (SLE) is the only organisation in the consultations analysed to mention the land use of shooting and stalking. Private goods – food and timber, for example – are mentioned by almost as many organisations. In this view, land is a basis for economic activity, providing personal but also local benefits such as employment or national benefits such as food security.

Environmental functions of land are sometimes presented as having economic or social benefits, such as forests that are carbon sinks while also providing spaces for recreation, tourism, and economic activity via timber harvesting (CONFOR, Highlands and Islands Enterprise). Soil Association speaks of “natural resources that underpin economic activity” supported by agroecological and organic farming (National Council of Rural Advisors consultation). Environmental functions of land are also proposed as major solutions to environmental problems: peatland and forests for carbon sequestration, space and resources for renewable energy, and various land uses and land cover for biodiversity and wildlife habitat. Overall, most organisations focus on the triumvirate of social, economic, and environmental functions; Quakers in Scotland alone speaks about the intrinsic and sacred value of land, not claiming that it needs a purpose to exist.

3.2 Sectoral vs holistic view

Organisations differ on whether issues are seen as discrete or systemic, involving only their sector (or another’s sector) or having links to other issues and sectors. For example, in the Good Food Nation consultation, the Soil Association and Scottish Crofters Federation (SCF) link food production to workers’ rights, health, waste, and other environmental impacts that need to be addressed systemically, while Scottish Land and Estates focuses solely on agricultural producers in their response to this particular consultation. The organisations also differ on whether they have chosen a narrow or wide range of issues to focus on. Paths for All has a narrow focus on issues to do with transport and walking in Scotland, but speaks for Scottish society as a whole, whereas CONFOR represents members of the forestry and wood supply chain and is almost solely concerned with promoting the increase of that sector in its responses. Finally, some organisations portray themselves as representing broader populations in their answers, others represent a definite cohort such as members. For example, HIE has a broader remit, representing people, communities and businesses in the region, focusing on economic success but also concerned with inclusion and environmental sustainability. National Farmers Union Scotland (NFUS) represents its members to ensure they benefit from any land use or regulation changes, although it also emphasises the importance of farming for wider communities.

Figure 1

3.3 Looking for change or supporting status quo?

Opinions on the extent of change needed range from narrow, isolated instances to wide-reaching and comprehensive change. Similarly, views on the degree of change needed range from tweaks to full systemic change. In this, many of the organisations tend to fall into categories. The environmental organisations – John Muir Trust, Scottish Environment LINK – advocate for system-wide, deep changes in land use. Scottish Environment Link claims, “We must make large scale and rapid changes in the way we use and manage our land” (Third Land Use Strategy consultation). Organisations representing community groups or interests – Community Land Scotland, Community Woodlands Association, and SCF – argue that transformative change is required by the climate and nature emergencies, food system crisis, and land ownership/agriculture status quo. Quakers in Scotland refers to “the fundamental reframing of our relationship with the natural world that is required” (Review of Land Rights and Responsibilities Statement consultation) from extractive, human-centred to being part of the natural world. Community Woodlands Association argues that “The main barrier to a just transition is the refusal of the sector and its regulators to recognise the scale of change needed” (Agricultural Transition in Scotland consultation). Established landed groups – NFUS and SLE – suggest that any changes needed are minor in scope and impact. They see less need for wide-reaching, significant, quick change and argue that changing culture and way of life will take a longer time. Rather than advocating for a wholesale change in the dominant model of agricultural production as Soil Association does, NFUS believes changes are needed to agri-environmental regulations towards performance-based payments. SLE supports a continuation of the model of land ownership and tenure, limiting the decision-making power of communities.

3.4 Environmental issues

Organisations differ on the extent to which they think environment-human interactions are negative or positive, what changes are needed, and what level of priority environmental issues should have. When they talk about causes, organisations typically attribute environmental problems to other sectors’ practices and/or offer proposals beneficial to their own sector as solutions. For example, CONFOR argues hill farming is a major GHG emitting practice and farmers should be encouraged to plant trees and Paths for All argues that denser housing with less need for car travel would positively impact on climate issues. Unsurprisingly, environmental organisations have a detailed list of concerns. Scottish Environment LINK is concerned with agriculture, impacts of the current economic model, and government on the environment. It refers to a range of environmental problems, including greenhouse gas emissions, pollinators and biodiversity, and restoration of native habitats. The Scottish Crofting Federation is concerned about climate change (emissions from ‘industrialised’ agriculture and from long supply chains) and biodiversity. Crofting is presented as being key for sustainable food production, tackling climate change and biodiversity. CONFOR is primarily concerned with climate change and offer trees as the solution, supported by government funding. It believes environmental and economic goals should complement and support each other. Community Land Scotland is concerned about environmental issues such as climate change and biodiversity but see them through a social lens such as Just Transition or land ownership. SLE briefly mentions climate change mitigation and seeks recognition for current activities, arguing that traditional landowners can deliver and fund environmental objectives.

3.5 Social justice issues

Significant social justice concerns focus on processes relating to land use. Many groups advocate for democratic participation in planning and decision-making, with special mention of inclusion of marginalised groups. The John Muir Trust sees a need to “overcome barriers to participation such as digital divides, unequal access to information, and also consider the different needs of individuals to participate or engage meaningfully” (Climate Change – Net Zero Nation consultation) and Royal Town Planning Institute (RTPI) notes “issues about how we ensure people have equal accessibility to the things they need” (Just Transition

Commission consultation). Another frequent concern is equality - access to land and fair distribution of wealth/benefits from land. Organisations frame their arguments using concepts such as community wealth, common good, public benefit, sustainable diets, and food security. A quote from Community Land Scotland encompasses all of these concerns:

“the principles of a Just Transition must be embedded throughout all actions. This must ensure that communities are actively engaged in land use decisions and that planning and public support for net zero does not widen existing inequalities. The opportunities and benefits arising from these actions must be shared fairly across Scotland.... through sustainable land and other asset management that retains wealth within communities on a more equitable basis for the common good” (Draft National Planning Framework 4 consultation)

As with the environment, some organisations, such as SLE and CONFOR, do not bring up social justice issues in a significant way. Others, such as Creative Scotland, focus mostly on their sector: they focus on accessibility in art, and on the role that land can play in this, particularly in terms of rural isolation and digital exclusion.

3.6 Rights vs responsibilities

Many organisations do not use the language of ‘rights and responsibilities’ but some do, and the concepts can be discerned even if not named as such. SLE advocates for the rights of private landowners rather than communities to decide on land use on private land, and NFUS stresses that farmers should be in a position where they can manage their land with minimal interference. In contrast, the Community Woodland Association argues that land right-holders have environmental and social responsibilities towards local communities. Decisions about land use should not be “limited to small, heavily subsidised groups of wealthy people” (Draft National Planning Framework 4 consultation). Scottish Environment LINK advocates for the rights of the Scottish public, including rights to food, and rights of farmers to be able to make a decent living.

There are differing beliefs about the responsibility of government. Established landed groups tend to want government to incentivize rather than obligate in circumstances where businesses won’t benefit financially from a change in practice – to use the carrot rather than the stick. The community-oriented groups often posit the government’s role as to ‘facilitate’ rather than ‘incentivize’. For example, the NFUS argues that all capital funding should be 50% government, 50% farmer unless it’s only for environmental benefits in which case the government should pay much more (Agricultural Transition in Scotland consultation). In contrast, the SCF argues that only public benefits should be funded by the public with perhaps government loans for private benefits.

To extent to which the organisations think responsibility for change is part of their role differs as well. There are some suggestions that the problem is for other sectors to solve, e.g., CONFOR states “Attempts to encourage farmers to diversify by planting some of their land must be intensified dramatically” (Support for Agricultural and the Rural Economy consultation) to meet climate change targets. On the other hand, NFUS is concerned that primary producers will carry most of the environmental responsibility and financial cost of environmental land use actions.

4 Interim conclusions

The positions taken by organisations regarding issues presented by the government in consultations consider different epistemic and spatial scales, from holistic and global to sectoral and localized. However, much of the current discourse is adversarial and narrowly focused. A multi-scalar approach – imbricated with multifunctionality – could help to enable an understanding of interlinked issues and a possibly more inclusive frame for land use changes.

While we cannot yet incorporate analysis of the interviews that are underway into this milestone report, anecdotally, the organisation representatives interviewed so far have confirmed that the analyses we shared with them of their future vision, based on consultation responses, have been accurate.

Based on his work in Scottish communities, Shucksmith (2018) suggests that encouraging “collective imagining of alternatives” (p. 164) is necessary to dislodge the status quo and assist radical, holistic thinking. He proposes that utopian thinking be incorporated in local, democratic planning processes for rural development. Once the interviews are complete, we will be able to assemble comprehensive future visions of land use in Scotland and consider what uses they may be put to.

5 Next steps

- Completion of the interviews related to the consultation responses (November 2023)
- Undertake selection process for representatives of lesser-heard, alternative voices on land use (November 2023)
- Begin making connections and building relationships with selected stakeholders (December-March 2023)
- Complete an ethics application for walking video interviews with stakeholders (January 2024)
- Briefing published on the outcomes of the consultation responses analysis and interviews (May 2024)

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